

Literature Review on Exactly What the Real Estate Contract Is and Its Role

Selman Ozgun, PhD

To cite this article: Selman ÖZGÜN, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 115 – 132. - 0099-0001-2209-0106.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia")

- The magazine is published monthly.

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

"" • Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

In real estate investing, it is necessary to explain exactly what a real estate contract is and what the various real estate contracts are called. What role these contracts play in the overall picture for real estate investments is a separate consideration. Real estate contracts fall into one of four categories: purchase agreements, title agreements, lease agreements, and power of attorney agreements. They are individually unique in their application and prerequisites. This article will discuss the many types of real estate contracts that supply the basic information you need to make educated choices about investing in real estate. When two or more people agree on the terms of a real estate transaction, that discussion is referred to in a document called a real estate contract. This document is legally binding and defines the terms of the transaction. Once both parties have signed a contract, the provisions set out in the document become legally binding. They often include information about real estate contingencies, the vehicles involved in the sale, the size of the deposit, who manages paying closing costs, and the date the transaction will take place. When you make a purchase as a real estate investor, you often find yourself having to negotiate and execute real estate contracts. In other words, the purpose of a real estate contract is to supply security for both buyers and sellers while making the process of buying a home more transparent. It can be important to keep this in mind when preparing to enter a real estate contract. The prospective buyer will

begin the process by sending a formal offer letter. The seller has the option of rejecting the offer or making a counteroffer where they can change aspects of the deal, such as the purchase price, closing costs, or contingencies. As a result, the real estate contract preparation process is now in the negotiation phase. After this point, the buyer will be given the choice to either change the terms or accept the added terms, which includes changing the same things as before. This procedure usually takes place between real estate agents being the buyer and seller. Whatever they choose to do in the end will form the basis of their real estate deal. This article includes literature review and reviews for details.

Keywords: *Real Estate Agreement, Quality of Real Estate Agreement, Properties of Real Estate Agreement, Real Estate, Real Estate Sector*

1. Introduction

Because a real estate deal is legally binding, Adam Garcia, founder of The Stock Dork, recommends collaborating with a skilled professional to protect your interests. According to Garcia, "it is a fact that every transaction must be made by persons who are legally qualified to undertake a contract." Once the status of a property is secured by a document signed by both parties to a real estate agreement, the contract then becomes legally enforceable. In other words, the act of signing and sealing a contract is the only way it gains the force of law. Contracts involving real estate are typically initialed by all parties involved in the transaction and then testify to the property being traded. For a contract to be considered legitimate, both parties must have an agreement so that it can be signed by both parties. If one of the parties makes a counteroffer, the first contract will not be legally valid since the terms of the contract are not mutually accepted by both parties. There are several actions that investors can take to increase the likelihood of successful execution of a real estate transaction. To begin, it is important that all parties fully understand the terms of the agreement. To do this, you will need to use language that everyone can understand, avoid using abbreviations, and evaluate the places that may cause confusion. Because of the time sensitive nature of many real estate transactions, investors need to make sure they include an end date on

their contracts. It is necessary to include the timelines within the contract as well as provisions on what happens if deadlines are missed (usually this will result in termination of the contract).

2. Contract Related to Real Estate

For a real estate contract to be valid, it must be signed by both the buyer and the seller. Both signatures are needed to create a legally binding document. It is possible for real estate agents to sign documents on behalf of their clients in certain circumstances (with consent). However, in almost all cases, it is the responsibility of both the buyer and the seller to sign the real estate contract to finalize the deal.

a. Real Estate Contract Requirements

For a real estate contract to be considered legally binding, as with most transactions, a few conditions must first be met. For real estate contracts to be valid, the following conditions must always be met:

In the form of a real estate contract, the first party will make an offer to buy the real estate to the second party. They must be written, signed, and then handed over to the other party. After that, the second party has the choice to either accept, decline, or counteroffer.

Acceptance: The second party signifies the purchase agreement for the property, showing that it accepts the offer. Contact is essential to have original signatures from both parties. Any adjustment that can be made by either party should be started. If you make a counteroffer, the earlier offer will be considered void and void and will not be legally binding on any of the parties involved. If the offer is rejected, the deal will end.

Consider the fact that both parties will supply something of equal or greater value to the other (most commonly in the form of money) in return. Another property or a promise to fulfill may alternatively function as consideration in this scenario.

Legal Capacity: Both parties must have legal ability to enter a real estate transaction. Minors, mentally handicapped and others fall under the category of persons who are not legally allowed to vote.

Legality of Purpose: *There* cannot be any unlawful provisions in the real estate contract.

b. What Should Be Included in the Real Estate Purchase Agreement?

Contracts are needed to complete many real estate transactions, and the terms of each contract will be unique. However, every real estate contract has a few components that are necessary, and you should be familiar with them. If you have a firm grasp of the necessary elements, you can help ensure that any agreement you make is complete and correct. The following is the list of subjects that should be included in different contracts and contracts related to real estate:

Price and Timing: The final agreed-upon purchase price of the property and the duration of the timeline for the transaction are the two most fundamental aspects that should be included in any real estate contract. In this part of the contract, you must explain when the conditions will be met and when the title will be changed. It is usual practice to begin a real estate contract with this information, as understanding it is essential to the proper completion of the purchase by both parties involved.

3. The Term "Conditions"

The term "conditions" refers to everything that needs to be done for the transaction to be successful. Depending on the type of emergency, the procedure and timeline for doing so will be different. For example, the seller may have to make certain repairs to the property in the time leading up to the closing period. If certain conditions are not met, either party may end the contract without further liability.

Unexpected situations related to home inspection are the ones that occur most often. Every real estate purchase contract should have a clause that gives the buyer the right to withdraw from the

deal if the results of the property inspection do not meet their expectations. Vendors should make it clear what repairs they must make before the closure takes place. If inspection information (and contingencies) is included in the contract, the buyer will be protected from being forced into a purchase for which he has not registered.

essential to include a possibility for buyers to withdraw from the deal if they are unable to secure financing . Depending on the circumstances, it's also a good idea to add a condition that protects the buyer if their old home doesn't sell.

It is important to clearly find who manages closing costs, and it is also important to keep track of information about this responsibility on an ongoing basis. In many transactions it is possible for sellers to pay these costs, but the terms of this arrangement may be hidden in the contract. To avoid misunderstandings, information about closing costs should be clarified in any real estate contract.

When offering a home for sale, some sellers may add a guarantee to the property for the peace of mind of the buyer. However, this is entirely up to the vendors and is expected to bear certain costs associated with repairs. If there is a warranty on the property, it should be included in the contract so that it is clear to both parties who is responsible.

4. Default in Contract

It is quite typical in real estate contracts to specify what would happen if one or more of the parties defaulted on the contract. This helps buyers and sellers have clear expectations of each other and avoids the need for legal action if either party doesn't live up to halfway through the contract. Since the repercussions of the default are included in the contract, there will be no "what if" question while signing the contract.

The section of the contract called "Riders and Attachments" will specify the extra information needed for the transaction. One of the most typical examples of a rider or addendum, if relevant, is information about a homeowner's association (HOA). Real estate purchase criteria and conditions should be specified in the contract in a way that is easily understood by the potential buyer.

It is necessary to be sure to include a note in the purchase agreement saying which of the existing appliances, if any, you wish to keep after the sale is complete. There is no assurance that a verbal agreement will suffice if you do not supply precise information about the household items that must be left in the residence.

5. Different Transaction Types in Real Estate

Contract agreements are needed to complete several different real estate transactions. Before going into the analysis of the many real estate contracts available, it is helpful to review the following categories of real estate transactions:

Buying a home: During your career as an investor, you may come across many different homes you would like to buy. It is possible to choose to cooperate with a purchasing agent who will help you find potential bargains through MLS, make offers on your behalf, and guide you through the purchasing contract.

If you are interested in owning a home and making money by renting, of course you will need to own properties that can be rented out to others to do so. This can include anything from apartment complexes with dozens of units to single-family homes.

plays a vital role in discovering non-market properties and transferring the purchase contract to an end buyer such as a rehabilitation specialist.

6. Prehabilitation of a Property

Prehabilitation of a property is a form of plan to leave in which an investor makes minor changes to a property, just enough to make it acceptable to another end buyer, such as a rehabilitation officer. Pre-rehabilitation of a property is also often referred to as "prehabilitation". Some people might argue that the prep process is the step that comes between wholesale and rehabilitation .

7. Different Types of Contracts Regarding Real Estate

As a real estate investor, it is essential that you have a solid understanding of the multitude of real estate deals and contracts you may meet throughout your career. The purpose of these agreements is to serve your best interests, such as protecting your assets and reducing the amount of risk and liability you are exposed to. It is also helpful to understand how the protections provided by these contracts work to protect the other party. You should currently educate yourself with the following four common real estate contracts:

The most typical type of real estate contract is known as a contract of purchase, although it is also called a contract of sale. This is, as the name suggests, a real estate contract that sets an agreement between the buyer and seller of a particular property. (“Types of Land Purchase Agreement - Kehf”) It may also be called a "purchase and sale contract". In this real estate contract form, the following parts are included as generally seen in contracts:

Most real estate associations serving state and local markets have standard purchase agreements that are used to manage transactions that take place within their organization. A general purchase agreement is a variation of a state or association purchase agreement that is significantly streamlined and often significantly shorter as a result. When dealing directly with sellers and not going through a real estate agent to buy a home, this real estate contract is an excellent choice to consider using.

8. Property-Specific Purchase Agreement

If you are buying a property that does not fit the standard mold of a single-family home, such as a mobile home or undeveloped land, you may need to enter into property-specific purchase agreements (this will depend on the market). Although these various purchase agreements have some similarities, each of the real estate agreements that fall into these categories has specific provisions about the type of property being exchanged.

A wholesale real estate investment strategy is the most common use of a real estate allocation agreement.

If you want to lock down a property with a purchase agreement and then transfer that property to someone else, you can do so using the "assigner" part of the contract. Even if added words don't take up much space in the printed document, they give you as an investor a significant amount of room for decision-making.

9. Rental Agreements

According to the terms of this real estate lease agreement, the property owner is obliged to present the unit to the tenant each month at a predetermined cost. Agreements of this nature include important aspects such as the monthly rent, the size of the security deposit, and how utilities will be managed. It is understood that leasing arrangements designed to protect both lessor and lessee if an unexpected situation should prevent future disputes between lessor and lessee.

Although power of attorney forms is not only used in the context of real estate transactions, but they are also considered a type of real estate contract and can be extremely helpful in a variety of situations. This is because this document authorizes another party to sign on your behalf if, for any reason, you are unable to sign a real estate contract for any reason, including being physically distant from the nation or mentally ill.

If you are a rental property owner or caring for an elderly parent or relative who may be facing a situation where they cannot sign their own property contract, this type of property agreement can be of immense help. You may find yourself in a situation where you must sign a real estate contract on their behalf. It is possible for the party or principle authorizing them to act on their behalf to have someone else sign it instead. It is possible for the manager to be one of the following:

A real estate contract need not be difficult or challenging to understand. Understanding the many types of real estate contracts available, how they can help you as an investor, and the terms in which they are most useful are smart places to start. If you are aware of this, you will be one step closer to becoming an expert investor.

Real estate business can be difficult because there are so many features and kinks that need to be fixed before you can move into a new property. Getting to the point where you can sign a contract

can be a difficult and time-consuming procedure . Once you've chosen the ideal home, secured financing, and made an offer to purchase property, it can be difficult to get to this point, among other steps.

However, when you finally decide to make a formal offer to buy the house you want to buy, you will need to read and fill out a substantial amount of paperwork outlining the terms and conditions of your offer. In addition to the more visible aspects of the transaction, such as the location of the property and the purchase price, the purchase contract for your real estate investment should include the following more complex aspects. These terms are referred to in legal jargon as "contingency" and are included in the contract for the purchase of your real estate.

It is difficult to cut all the variables and gather all the proper documents and funds in such a brief time, but sometimes the buyer or seller can request a closing that takes place in two weeks or less. Oftentimes, the delay is neither the buyer nor the seller; rather, the bottlenecks are the lender or insurer, the title company or the lawyers.

10. Sale of an Already Used Property

While there are many more components that make up a comprehensive real estate contract, most of these components should not give you any significant cause for concern. Standardized, fill-in-the-blank forms that cover all the basics and are often used by real estate agents are examples of the types of forms detailed in this article.

While these forms are common and standardized, and a good real estate agent won't let you leave anything important out of your contract, it's still a good idea to educate yourself about the basic components of a real estate purchase agreement.

As a direct result of this, the entire history of each transaction is visible to any member of the network. It is difficult to hide earlier owners or changes made to an item.

11. Faster Processing of Financial Transactions

It is a known fact that transactions involving real estate take a lot of time. A transaction can take from a few weeks to several months or even years to complete. Boredom can easily be avoided by using a simple smart contract for real estate transaction. Computerization, both precise and well thought out, has replaced cumbersome bureaucracy and head-scratching. As the process is done automatically, both potential investors and property owners experience a modern procedure .

When it comes to real estate, the use of smart contracts helps reduce costs while also giving buyers and sellers more flexibility. This is because only interested parties can decide the final parameters of an agreement.

The availability of a partial ownership option is often essential to the success of a real estate venture. It makes it easier for investors to seize the asset, streamlines the process of doing so, diversifies the investor 's portfolio , and supplies a host of added benefits along the way.

Smart contracts in the real estate industry encourage fragmentation as any asset can be tokenized and split into parts or segments that can then be exchanged separately. This allows the entire asset to be traded. In the same breath, multiple buyers and sellers can be parties to a smart contract at the same time, and the number of potential investors is by no means limited.

There are already examples of practical solutions for fragmented investments in the global real estate market. These solutions allow people to buy stock segments valued at one hundred dollars or more.

12. Improved liquidity

The real estate market is notorious for having low levels of liquidity for a variety of reasons, including many market entry restrictions, complex access, difficult and time-consuming transaction processes, and more. The implementation of a smart contract for real estate will increase the liquidity of the asset as transactions will not take months to complete, ease the partial ownership trading mechanism and the property will become available to buyers all over the world. Therefore, a company owner who places his bets on tokenization and smart contracts helps better liquidity of the asset by making such bets.

The claim that any smart contract in the real estate industry is hack proof is not supported by reasoning. On the other hand, if an entrepreneur chooses an experienced IT vendor who adheres to the best security standards (pentests, security checks, vulnerability scanners, etc.), there will be no need to worry about cybersecurity.

Another useful feature any entrepreneur would want is increased backup, which is often an essential part. The thing is, since smart contracts are built on Blockchain, they copy all transactions. This means that even if anything happens with a single device, the data will still be accessible over the network. Therefore, it is physically impossible to lose them forever .

Parties wishing to reach an agreement can use the platform to perform and track many transactions, including the sale, purchase and lease of real estate.

All provisions of the SMARTRealty smart contract for real estate must be extensively discussed and agreed upon by all relevant parties for the contract to be considered valid. After all the conditions are clarified and understood, SMARTRealty will create a smart contract that will manage the parties' relations with each other. The fulfillment of the variable programmed into an agreement (for example, the successful receipt of the final payment) is what starts the execution of the agreement. Participants have the choice to renew the existing contract or enter a new one, depending on the circumstances.

The marketplace uses Blockchain technology to enable secure exchange of tokenized real estate and to give tokenized incentives in the form of micropayments to active users to take active actions. In this case, digital transactions in the real estate sector are conducted with the help of a smart contract. The platform uses the well-known cryptocurrency Bitcoin, in addition to its own cryptocurrency known as Property Club Coin, to provide customers with the highest level of convenience (PPC) . In 2020, the firm formed a partnership with an Ethereum software supplier to complete a transaction that will have a significant impact on the worldwide real estate market and tokenize assets worth more than 350 million euros. It's important to keep in mind that this isn't the biggest real estate tokenization ever. As an example, in 2019 Liquefy claimed that they would

tokenize a five-star hotel in London valued at over \$600 million. Despite this, the project that Mata Capital is working on stays one of the most remarkable and influential.

The primary reason for this is that it is an ideal business case example as it depicts the active adoption of Blockchain technologies by corporate participants in the real estate industry. In addition, it proves that contemporary technology can be user-friendly and seamlessly bring businesses and individual investors together. A few years ago, the idea of using smart contracts during real estate transactions was first introduced. The technology known as blockchain is no longer just jargon, nor is it a hypothetical magic wand to fulfill the desires of the chosen few . In 2022, contracts powered by blockchain technology have turned into well-established and incredibly valuable tools from which participants in the real estate market can profit. The most obvious benefits appreciated by every entrepreneur are increased transparency, cost-effectiveness, improved security, greater accuracy, clearer communication and the absence of middlemen.

The current state of the global Blockchain market shows that smart contracts in the real estate industry have dozens of use models and can be used in both business-to-business and business-to-consumer business models.

If you are considering adopting smart contracts and implementing them in your company, you need to find a dependable software development partner who can manage the technical aspects for you. This is a prerequisite for progress in the concept . Since the beginning of this decade, there has been a growing interest in the principles behind Bitcoin as well as Blockchain applications. The term "blockchain" was first coined in 2008 by an anonymous person under the pseudonym "Satoshi Nakamoto", who detailed how cryptography and an open distributed ledger could be combined in one application for digital currency. Blockchain's main attributes that allow anonymity, security, and integrity without relying on trusted third-party organizations have been the driving force of the growing interest in Blockchain research. All economies and financial systems are now going through digital transformation as an ongoing trend. In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in blockchain technology based on cryptography. This interest has been spurred by the rise of cryptocurrencies . The term "blockchain" refers to both a distributed

database and a public ledger. Information recorded on the blockchain and made publicly available relates to any transactions, contracts or assets involving virtual currencies. The data is first recorded and then sealed with a timestamp before being encrypted together. Following this, a hash value will be calculated and saved in a data block. Because it is built on a cryptographic system, the blockchain is resistant to easy modification or deletion. This makes blockchain very secure. A blockchain is a blockchain that has information, each of which is accessible to everyone and can be accessed without restrictions. The sender sends the encrypted communication to the receiver using the receiver's public key. These messages can only be decrypted using the recipient's private key. One of the most fundamental features of a contemporary economy and the digital revolution that has occurred in the last few years is the transition to the field of blockchain technology and smart contracts. In this article, we conduct a literature review to find and explore existing research linked to Blockchain-based smart contracts specifically for real estate .

Until recently, the only application developed and researched for blockchain technology was cryptocurrencies . But with the release of Ethereum, which enables the creation and execution of smart contracts, applications that go beyond cryptocurrencies are now being developed and researched. A smart contract is a contract that has the terms of the contract between the buyer and the seller. The contract defines pre-programmed contract rules so that its execution takes effect when the input data meets the conditions provided.

13. Smart Contracts

Electronic contracts, also known as smart contracts, are a digital alternative to the traditional method of verifying legal documents. Smart contracts can be defined as the digital verification of legal documents. Contracts are created in a programming language called Solidity, which is specifically designed for use in such computer systems. Using a cryptographic hash algorithm known as SHA 256 in a distributed and decentralized blockchain network, where code controls execution and transactions are both irreversible and traceable, smart contracts make it possible to distribute trusted transactions and agreements among multiple parties. The need for a central legal system or authority. Shape presents a variety of architectural components; Below is a list of such

components. A new block is generated containing information about the transaction. The block is broadcast to each node that is part of the network. The Transaction Block will be added to the already existing blockchain. The number of the earlier block in the chain; each block has a reference to the block that preceded it in the chain, allowing all associated blocks to examine the entire history.

14. Conclusion

After encryption and data validation, the process will generate a nonce because of the aid of the cryptographic hash technique (SHA 256). Smart contracts allowed the digital transfer of properties from one internet user to another so that assets remained safe and secure. To find the importance of smart contracts based on blockchain technology, the purpose of this article is to review and discuss earlier research, compile their findings, and supply a summary of empirical evidence on blockchain technology and applications of smart contracts. The most important thing we can draw from these scientific studies is to show how to integrate this work and earlier work, which is arranged from the most recent to the oldest work . Some earlier studies about the research were reviewed and discussed (for example, theses and conference proceedings). The literature review is based on an advanced electronic search conducted in 2021 using IEEE, Elsevier, Emerald, Science Direct, and Springer Link alongside currently accessible books on the topic.

15. References

- Anglin, P., and R. Arnott. (1991). "Residential Real Estate Brokerage as a Principal-Agent Problem," *Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics* Vol. 4.99–125.
- Arnott, R. (1989). "Housing Vacancies, Thin Markets and Idiosyncratic Tastes," *Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics* Vol. 2.5–30.
- British Monopolies Commission. (1969). *A Report on the Supply of Certain Services by Estate Agents*, Her Majesty's Stationery Office, London, England.
- British Prices Commission. (1979). *Charges, Costs and Margins of Estate Agents*, Her Majesty's Stationery Office, London, England.

- Bureau of Competition Policy. (1988). "Real Estate Inquiry," Consumer and Corporate Affairs Canada, Ottawa, Canada.
- Doiron, J., J. Shilling, and C. Sirmans. (1985). "Owner versus Broker Sales: Evidence on the Amount of the Brokerage Commission Capitalized," Real Estate Appraiser and Analyst Vol. 51, No. 4, 44–48.
- Erxleben, W. (1981). "In Search of Price and Service Competition in Residential Real Estate Brokerage: Breaking the Cartel," Washington Law Review Vol. 56, 179–215.
- Federal Trade Commission. (1983). The Residential Real Estate Brokerage Industry, Volumes I and II, US Government Printing Office, Los Angeles. ("Residential real estate brokerage as a principal-agent problem") ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink")
- Geltner, D., B. Kluger, and N. Miller. (1991). "Optimal Price and Selling Effort from the Perspective of the Broker and Seller," AREUEA Journal Vol. 19, 1–24. ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink") ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink")
- Haurin, D. (1989). "The Duration of Marketing Time of Residential Housing," AREUEA Journal Vol. 17, 396–410.
- Jud, D., and J. Frew. (1986). "Real Estate Brokers, Housing Prices and the Demand for Housing," Urban Studies Vol. 23, 21–31. ("Real Estate Brokerage and the Housing Market: An Annotated ... - CORE") ("Real Estate Brokerage and the Housing Market: An Annotated ... - CORE")
- Knoll, M. (1988). "Uncertainty and Efficiency in the Brokerage Industry," Journal of Law and Economics Vol. 31, 249–263. ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink") ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink")
- Larsen, J., and W. Park. (1989). "Non-uniform Percentage Brokerage Commissions and Real Estate Market Performance," AREUEA Journal Vol. 17, 422–438. ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink") ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink")
- Lone, AH and R. Naaz, Applicability of Blockchain smart contracts in securing Internet and IoT: a systematic literature review. ("Rohie Naaz Mir - Google Scholar") Computer Science Review, 2021. 39: p. 100360.
- Miceli, T. (1989). "The Optimal Duration of Real Estate Listing Contracts," AREUEA Journal Vol. 17, 267–277. ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink") ("Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink")

- Miller, N., and P. Shedd. (1979). “Do Antitrust Laws Apply to the Real Estate Brokerage Industry,” *American Business Law Journal* Vol. 17, 313–339.
- Nakamoto, S., Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system. *Decentralized Business Review*, 2008: p. 21260/
- Rubinstein, A., and A. Wolinsky. (1987). “Middlemen,” *Quarterly Journal of Economics* Vol. 102, 581–593.
- Schroeter, J. (1987). “Competition and Value of Service Pricing in Residential Real Estate Brokerage Market,” *Quarterly Review of Economics and Business* Vol. 27, 29–40. (“Residential real estate brokerage as a principal-agent problem”) (“Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink”)
- Unal, D., M. Hammoudeh, and MS Kiraz, Policy specification and verification for blockchain and smart contracts in 5G networks. (“Devrim Ünal - Google Scholar”) (“Integration of federated machine learning and blockchain for the ...”) *ICT Express*, 2020. 6(1): p. 43-47. 5. Yadav, SP, Blockchain Security, in *Blockchain Security in Cloud Computing*. 2022, Springer. p. 1-18.
- Vacca, A., et al., A systematic literature review of blockchain and smart contract development: Techniques, tools, and open challenges. (“References — CBC”) (“References — CBC”) *Journal of Systems and Software*, 2020: p. 110891.
- Yavas, A. (1992). “A Simple Search and Bargaining Model of Real Estate Markets,” *AREEUEA Journal* Vol. 20, 533–548. (“Contracts for the sale of residential real estate | SpringerLink”)
- Zumpano, L., H. Elder, and G. Crellin. (1993). “The Market for Residential Brokerage Services: Costs of Production and Economies of Scale,” *Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics* Vol. 6, 237–250.